

Pre-trained Time Series Foundation Models for Traffic Flow Prediction Using Open Government Data: The case of Attica traffic OGD

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Abstract

Rapid urbanization and increase in vehicular traffic in metropolitan areas necessitate advanced predictive models to enhance traffic management systems. Open Government Data (OGD) portals provide accessible, high-quality traffic datasets, offering a valuable resource for developing and evaluating such models. This paper investigates the effectiveness of pre-trained Time Series Foundation Models, specifically Lag-Llama, in forecasting urban traffic flow using open government traffic data from the Greek OGD portal. We assess Lag-Llama's performance in both zero-shot and fine-tuned settings and compare it with traditional deep learning models, including Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs). Our experimental results demonstrate that Lag-Llama, especially when fine-tuned on traffic OGD, outperforms conventional models in prediction accuracy. These findings highlight the potential of combining foundation models with traffic open government data to advance intelligent transportation systems and contribute to the development of more robust and reliable traffic forecasting models, as well as provide innovative and efficient public services for citizens and businesses.

Keywords

Foundation Models, Traffic forecasting, Open Government Data, Foundation Models for Time Series, Large Language Models

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1 Introduction

The United Nations estimate that by 2050, 68% of the world's population will live in urban areas [40]. Poor urban development and unsustainable urbanization, particularly in large metropolitan areas, have led to an unprecedented number of vehicles traveling across road networks [13], causing long-time traffic congestions, increased air pollution[28], and a decline in employee productivity [24]. Traffic prediction is a critical component of Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) [23], which aims to predict future traffic features, including traffic flow, using specific amounts of historical data. Its purpose is to forecast future patterns, trends, and events in various aspects of urban life, contributing to numerous applications including road traffic management, prediction of traffic congestion, prevention and detection of accidents, travel time estimation and many more [21].

In recent years, advances in data collection technologies, ranging from road sensors and cameras to GPS-enabled devices and smartphones, have provided governments with unprecedented access to real-time information on vehicle movements, congestion levels, and traffic flow patterns. Many countries, including Greece have started providing traffic-related data as Open Government Data (OGD) through their national portals [18]. OGD, including open traffic data, is recognized as high-value data (HVD) that creates economic growth, promotes innovation, and increases transparency of administration [20]. Given the advanced capabilities of new Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems, it is critical that these traffic OGD portals deliver unambiguous datasets with sufficiently detailed metadata, in standardized, machine-readable formats and updated in real-time. This is because AI systems, thanks to their learning capabilities, can, in contrast to earlier generations of ITSs, act autonomously and even self-modify their behaviour or even be effective in downstream tasks without the need of training (zero shot). Furthermore, traffic OGD are open and easily accessible through Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), enabling researchers to retrieve the necessary traffic information without undergoing procedures that

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include restricted authorization protocols. They are often updated in real time, providing up-to-date traffic information for analysis and prediction and allow for the evaluation and experimentation of relevant models that are currently applied on commonly used benchmarking preprocessed datasets, such as the well known benchmarking dataset for traffic forecasting of California¹. With the advent of foundation models, which require pretraining on vast amounts of data, access to large-scale, diverse datasets, particularly from different cities and urban environments, has become increasingly important for capturing the variety of traffic patterns. To this end, it is anticipated that traffic ODG will contribute to the development of more robust and reliable traffic prediction models, as well as provide innovative and efficient public services for citizens and businesses.

Traffic prediction methods have evolved significantly over time. Statistical approaches such as Auto-Regressive Moving Average (ARMA) and its variants[42, 43] were initially applied for short-term traffic flow prediction, suitable for simple traffic systems but limited in handling complex data. As technology advanced and the rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) revolutionized data-driven approaches, machine learning models such as Support Vector Regression (SVR)[6], K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)[44] and ANNs[8] gained popularity, leveraging richer data sources but struggling with the intricate spatial-temporal relationships in large-scale traffic networks[46]. It was not until the advent of deep learning-based methods that the full potential of traffic prediction began to be realized[27]. With advancements in computational resources, deep learning models such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and its variants (Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU))[11], Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)[37], and spatial-temporal Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)[4] have demonstrated a superior ability to capture complex spatial-temporal dependencies inherent in traffic data. Especially, GNNs have been particularly effective in representing road networks (or sensor networks) as graphs, allowing for the modeling of interactions between different geographical data points [19] or connected road segments and improving the prediction accuracy in large-scale traffic networks[2, 15].

Pretrained foundation models including large language models (LLMs), have recently been applied in language[33] and image processing domains[29], demonstrating remarkable few-shot and even zero-shot generalization capabilities[3]. Recently, these models have demonstrated their adaptability to other kinds of modalities and domains, beyond text or images, including time series.

This paper aims to explore the effectiveness of pre-trained Time Series Foundation Models, specifically Lag-Llama [31], in predicting urban traffic flow using open government data. We assess the performance of Lag-Llama in both zero-shot and fine-tuned settings and compare it with traditional deep learning models utilizing traffic data from the data.gov.gr portal. Our objective is to determine whether foundation models for time series can offer superior performance in traffic prediction tasks, thereby advancing the capabilities of intelligent transportation systems. Moreover, our study aims to explore the potential significance of open government data

in advancing intelligent transportation systems by providing accessible, high-quality datasets necessary for training and evaluating advanced AI models. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the background that is essential for this work. Section 3 presents the methodology of this work. Section 4 discusses the results and the various models' predictive performance. Finally, Section 5 concludes with the findings and potential future research directions.

2 Background

2.1 Foundation Models

Pre-trained foundation models (PFMs) are a class of deep models that are pretrained on vast amounts of data and can be adapted to solve a wide range of downstream tasks. The core innovation of PFMs lies in the adoption of the Transformer architecture [41] and the utilization of the attention mechanism which allows the model to dynamically focus on different parts of the input data. Besides attention mechanism's capability to learn global, long-range dependencies in data, Transformer's architecture enables efficient parallelization during computation operations, allowing these models to process massive datasets using self-supervised or unsupervised learning techniques. Consequently, they have the ability to learn broad, transferable knowledge across domains such as language and vision. For instance, LLMs have demonstrated great performance in learning complex semantic and knowledge representations from vast amounts of text data. The achievements of models such as GPT-4[1], Llama [38] and T5[30] in natural language understanding and generation have sparked interest in investigating their potential to work with complex, multimodal datasets that extend beyond conventional language-based domains. In computer vision, foundational models like the text-prompted CLIP [29] and the visually-prompted SAM [22] have driven significant advancements in areas such as image recognition and object detection.

2.2 Foundation Models for Time Series

Time series data are characterized by their sequential order and temporal or spatial-temporal dependencies, containing valuable insights into the dynamics of various systems and processes. They are prevalent across numerous real-world applications including transportation[16], finance[39], energy [48] and healthcare [14]. In recent years, inspired by the success of foundation models in fields like NLP and computer vision, the concept of Time Series Foundation Models (TSFMs) has emerged as a promising new direction for time series analysis[25]. These models, following the paradigm of other foundation models, can be either pre-trained from scratch on large-scale and diverse time series data, fine-tuned on specific time series tasks or even deployed directly in a zero-shot setting. For the context of this work, TSFMs are categorized in large pre-trained from scratch foundation models and approaches that leverage existing pre-trained FMs from other domains, commonly LLMs.

Lag-Llama [31] is a foundation model pretrained on a diverse corpus of time series data from various domains and designed for univariate probabilistic time series forecasting, using a decoder-only transformer architecture with lags as covariates. Another decoder-only approach is TimesFM [9] using input patching and a

¹<https://dot.ca.gov/programs/traffic-operations/mpr/pems-source>

large time-series corpus comprising both real-world and synthetic datasets. In contrast, Time-GPT [12] utilizes an encoder-decoder transformer architecture harnessing attention mechanisms to capture the diversity of past events and correctly extrapolate potential future distributions. TSMixer [10] on the other hand do not rely on transformer architecture, rather it is exclusively composed of multi-layer perceptron (MLP) modules for multi-variate time series forecasting. Other interesting approaches include the diffusion based models TimeGrad and TransFusion [32, 35] as well as STEP [34] which uses novel Graph Neural Network models along with a pre-trained transformer for efficient spatial-temporal forecasting.

Due to the fact that training a model from scratch is resource-intensive and heavily expensive, researchers have focused on alternative approaches leveraging remarkable pre-trained models from other domains, mainly LLMs. The various models developed can be categorized based on their methodological approaches to integrating time series data into LLMs and using existing LLM architectures on generating continuous time series forecasts. For example, TEMPO-GPT[5] decomposes time series data into seasonal and trend components and incorporates these into prompts that guide a GPT model. TIME-LLM [17] converts numerical time series data into textual representations before feeding it into a frozen LLM. OFA [47] employs a frozen GPT-2 model across various time series tasks and directly applies LLM capabilities to time series data by adapting the inputs, without modifying the LLM itself. TEST [36] creates specialized embeddings that capture various aspects of time series data, representing time series tokens effectively. The above models focus only on the temporal dimension of the data and ignore the spatial dependencies usually found in time series. For example, GATGPT [7] maintains most of the LLM parameters unchanged and integrate it with a Graph Attention module, enhancing LLM’s ability to understand spatial dependencies, while ST-LLM [26] transforms timesteps at each spatial location into tokens fusing them in a partially frozen LLM.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

Traffic data available from data.gov.gr (accessed on 12 October 2024) were collected using the data.gov.gr API. These data were gathered from sensors located throughout the Attica region in Greece. Additionally, the sensors’ positions were identified and mapped using geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude). Data.gov.gr serves as the official Greek open-government data (OGD) portal. The latest version, launched in 2020, offers access to 49 datasets published by various public entities, including central government agencies, local authorities, and other Greek public bodies. These datasets are organized into ten thematic categories, such as environment, economy, and transportation.

Using the data.gov.gr API, we collected 1,048,576 traffic records, from 352 sensors over a nine-month period, from 2 August 2022 to 30 April 2023. Figure 1 presents a snapshot of the traffic data. Figure 2 depicts the traffic flow at each sensor across Athens on December 25, 2022, at 14:00. Each record includes the sensor’s unique identifier (e.g., "MS734"), the road where the sensor is located, a detailed text description of its position, the date and time of the measurement (with hourly frequencies), the number of vehicles detected by the

sensor during the measurement hour and their average speed in km/h. For this work we utilized only the traffic flows, datetime and the positions of all sensors acquired from a previous study.

3.2 Traffic Flow forecasting

To explore the performance of Time Series Foundation models using traffic OGD, we use an open-source pre-trained foundation model for time series forecasting, namely Lag-Llama [31] and compare it with other two baselines, one simple LSTM for traffic forecasting and a state-of-the-art spatio-temporal GNN [45]. Our evaluation method consists of the following setting. We fine-tune Lag-Llama on the specific traffic dataset and particularly using 80% of the original data. Fine-tuning in this work primarily involves training the Lag-Llama pretrained model on the traffic dataset and tuning hyperparameters such as the learning rate and context length. The other supervised deep learning models are trained on the same amount of data and all of them are evaluated on the unseen test data which comprises 10% of the original dataset, while 10% is used for validation. Furthermore, we evaluate zero-shot capabilities of Lag-Llama (when no samples of the traffic dataset are provided for fine-tuning) on the same test set. All models are trained for 200 epochs using an early stopping criterion of 30 epochs. Following typical evaluation setups in traffic forecasting literature, all results reported in the paper are on the entire test set (last month of the original dataset). As a result, we adapt the evaluation process of the original paper of Lag-llama and evaluate the model on each single day of the test set. Due to limitation in resources, we evaluate all models on short-term forecasting, predicting 3 time steps ahead (3 hours) and mid-term forecasting, predicting 6 time steps ahead (6 hours). For evaluating the performance of the models, we employ two commonly used metrics: Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). These metrics are computed as follows:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_t - \hat{y}_t)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|y_t - \hat{y}_t|}{y_t} * 100 \quad (2)$$

where y_t denotes the real traffic flow and \hat{y}_t the corresponding predicted value. For all the models trained in this paper, we use a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 GPU.

4 Results

Table 1 presents the evaluation results comparing the performance of supervised baselines, LSTM and T-GCN—trained, on the training dataset and evaluated on the test set, alongside the zero-shot and fine-tuned performances of Lag-Llama. The models are assessed on both 3 and 6 time steps ahead prediction tasks using RMSE and MAPE as evaluation metrics, where lower values indicate better performance.

In the zero-shot setting, Lag-Llama attains performance comparable to all baselines. For 3 steps ahead prediction, Lag-Llama achieves an RMSE of 239.08, outperforming both LSTM (336.75) and T-GCN (309.42). However, its MAPE of 0.31 is slightly higher than the baselines. In the 6 steps ahead prediction, zero-shot Lag-Llama records an RMSE of 338.22 and a MAPE of 0.32, surpassing both

deviceid	countedcars	appprocesstime	road_name	road_info	average_speed
MS394	432	2022-08-02T00:00:00Z	ΒΑΣ. ΣΟΦΙΑΣ	ΚΥΡΙΟΣ ΔΡΟΜΟΣ ΜΕ ΚΑΤΕΥΘΥΝΣΗ ΚΕΝΤΡΟ 100 Μ. ΠΡΙΝ...	48.853659
MS434	641	2022-08-02T00:00:00Z	Λ. ΜΕΣΟΓΕΙΩΝ	ΚΥΡΙΟΣ ΔΡΟΜΟΣ ΜΕ ΚΑΤΕΥΘΥΝΣΗ ΠΡΟΣ ΑΓ. ΠΑΡΑΣΚΕΥΗ...	44.975610
MS435	619	2022-08-02T00:00:00Z	Λ. ΜΕΣΟΓΕΙΩΝ	ΚΕΝΤΡΙΚΟΣ ΚΛΑΔΟΣ ΜΕ ΚΑΤΕΥΘΥΝΣΗ Λ. ΒΑΣ. ΣΟΦΙΑΣ ...	43.926829
MS436	803	2022-08-02T00:00:00Z	ΦΕΙΔΙΠΠΙΔΟΥ	ΚΥΡΙΟΣ ΔΡΟΜΟΣ ΜΕ ΚΑΤΕΥΘΥΝΣΗ ΑΝΑΤΟΛΙΚΑ 80 Μ. ΠΡ...	43.121951
MS437	429	2022-08-02T00:00:00Z	Λ. ΜΕΣΟΓΕΙΩΝ	ΚΥΡΙΟΣ ΔΡΟΜΟΣ ΜΕ ΚΑΤΕΥΘΥΝΣΗ ΚΕΝΤΡΟ (ΝΔ) ΠΡΙΝ Α...	54.585366
...
MS946	941	2022-12-30T06:00:00Z	Π. ΡΑΛΛΗ	ΚΥΡΙΟΣ ΔΡΟΜΟΣ ΜΕ ΚΑΤΕΥΘΥΝΣΗ ΑΘΗΝΑ 40 Μ. ΠΡΙΝ Α...	19.894737
MS945	178	2022-12-30T06:00:00Z	Λ. ΚΗΦΙΣΟΥ	ΡΑΜΠΑ ΕΞΟΔΟΥ ΠΡΟΣ Π. ΡΑΛΛΗ ΤΟΥ ΚΛΑΔΟΥ ΤΗΣ Λ. Κ...	24.052632

Figure 1: A snapshot of the traffic data from data.gov.gr.

Figure 2: View of the 352 sensors in Athens on December 25, 2022, at 14:00. Each sensor is represented by a marker, where the size reflects the traffic intensity (larger markers indicate higher traffic), and the color transitions from green (low traffic) to red (high traffic).

baselines in RMSE and matching T-GCN in MAPE. This indicates that Lag-Llama, even without fine-tuning, can generalize well to unseen data, showcasing its potential as a robust foundation model.

Upon fine-tuning, Lag-Llama achieves state-of-the-art performance on both prediction horizons. For the 3 steps ahead prediction, it attains the lowest RMSE of 171.15 and the lowest MAPE of 0.21, significantly outperforming LSTM and T-GCN. Similarly, in the

6 steps ahead prediction, fine-tuned Lag-Llama records an RMSE of 242.78 and a MAPE of 0.28, again achieving the best results among all models. The fine-tuning process notably reduces the RMSE by up to 165 points compared to LSTM and by 138 points compared to T-GCN in the 3-step prediction task. Moreover, figures 3a, 3b demonstrate the performance of the fine-tuned Lag-Llama model, where the median forecast closely follows the actual data trends for both sensors over the entire test period, although minor discrepancies are visible in some regions of both time series.

Table 1: Evaluation results of zero-shot and fine-tuned Lag-Llama compared to supervised baselines for 3 and 6 time steps ahead prediction. Lower values of both MAPE and RMSE indicate greater performance.

Model	3 Steps		6 Steps	
	RMSE	MAPE	RMSE	MAPE
LSTM	336.75	0.37	459.77	0.42
T-GCN	309.42	0.29	404.42	0.33
Lag-Llama (zero-shot)	239.08	0.31	338.22	0.32
Lag-Llama (fine-tuned)	171.15	0.21	242.78	0.28

5 Conclusion

In this study, we explored the application of pretrained Time Series Foundation Models, specifically Lag-Llama, for predicting urban traffic flow using open government data from the data.gov.gr portal. Our experiments demonstrated that Lag-Llama, even in a zero-shot setting, performs comparably to traditional models like LSTM and spatio-temporal GNNs. After fine-tuning, Lag-Llama significantly outperforms these models, achieving state-of-the-art results in both short-term and longer-term traffic forecasting tasks. These findings suggest that foundation models possess a strong capability to capture complex temporal patterns inherent in traffic data, even without task-specific training. They also underscore the effectiveness of combining foundation models with open government data to capture complex temporal patterns inherent in traffic data. By leveraging such models and openly available datasets, intelligent transportation systems can be significantly improved, leading to better traffic management and reduced congestion in urban areas. We recommend that governments continue to support open data initiatives, ensuring that high-quality, real-time traffic data is available for research and development. Future research could extend this work by incorporating additional spatial-temporal factors, experimenting with other foundation models, and integrating these approaches into real-time traffic monitoring systems to further enhance urban mobility solutions.

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References

- [1] Josh Achiam, Steven Adler, Sandhini Agarwal, Lama Ahmad, Ilge Akkaya, Florencia Leoni Aleman, Diogo Almeida, Janko Altenschmidt, Sam Altman, Shyamal Anadkat, et al. 2023. Gpt-4 technical report. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.08774* (2023).
- [2] Petros Brimos, Areti Karamanou, Evangelos Kalampokis, and Konstantinos Tarabanis. 2023. Graph Neural Networks and Open-Government Data to Forecast Traffic Flow. *Information* 14, 4 (2023). doi:10.3390/info14040228
- [3] Tom B Brown. 2020. Language models are few-shot learners. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2005.14165* (2020).
- [4] Khac-Hoai Nam Bui, Jiho Cho, and Hongsuk Yi. 2022. Spatial-temporal graph neural network for traffic forecasting: An overview and open research issues. *Applied Intelligence* 52, 3 (2022), 2763–2774.
- [5] Defu Cao, Furong Jia, Sercan O Arik, Tomas Pfister, Yixiang Zheng, Wen Ye, and Yan Liu. 2023. Tempo: Prompt-based generative pre-trained transformer for time series forecasting. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.04948* (2023).
- [6] Manoel Castro-Neto, Young-Seon Jeong, Myong-Keel Jeong, and Lee D Han. 2009. Online-SVR for short-term traffic flow prediction under typical and atypical traffic conditions. *Expert systems with applications* 36, 3 (2009), 6164–6173.
- [7] Yakun Chen, Xianzhi Wang, and Guandong Xu. 2023. Gt-gpt: A pre-trained large language model with graph attention network for spatiotemporal imputation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.14332* (2023).
- [8] Alfréd Csikós, Zsolt János Viharos, Krisztián Balázs Kis, Tamás Tettamanti, and István Varga. 2015. Traffic speed prediction method for urban networks—An ANN approach. In *2015 International conference on models and technologies for intelligent transportation systems (MT-ITS)*. IEEE, 102–108.
- [9] Abhimanyu Das, Weihao Kong, Rajat Sen, and Yichen Zhou. 2023. A decoder-only foundation model for time-series forecasting. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.10688* (2023).
- [10] Vijay Ekambaram, Arindam Jati, Nam Nguyen, Phanwadee Sinthong, and Jayant Kalagnanam. 2023. Tsmixer: Lightweight mlp-mixer model for multivariate time series forecasting. In *Proceedings of the 29th ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. 459–469.
- [11] Rui Fu, Zuo Zhang, and Li Li. 2016. Using LSTM and GRU neural network methods for traffic flow prediction. In *2016 31st Youth academic annual conference of Chinese association of automation (YAC)*. IEEE, 324–328.
- [12] Azul Garza, Cristian Challu, and Max Mergenthaler-Canseco. 2023. TimeGPT-1. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.03589* (2023).
- [13] Omid Ghaffarpasand, Mohammad Reza Talaie, Hossein Ahmadikia, Amirreza TalaieKhozani, Maryam Davari Shalamzari, and Sina Majidi. 2021. How does unsustainable urbanization affect driving behavior and vehicular emissions? Evidence from Iran. *Sustainable Cities and Society* 72 (2021), 103065. doi:10.1016/j.scs.2021.103065
- [14] Hrayr Harutyunyan, Hrant Khachatryan, David C Kale, Greg Ver Steeg, and Aram Galstyan. 2019. Multitask learning and benchmarking with clinical time series data. *Scientific data* 6, 1 (2019), 96.
- [15] Weiwei Jiang and Jiayun Luo. 2022. Graph neural network for traffic forecasting: A survey. *Expert systems with applications* 207 (2022), 117921.
- [16] Guangyin Jin, Yuxuan Liang, Yuchen Fang, Zezhi Shao, Jincai Huang, Junbo Zhang, and Yu Zheng. 2023. Spatio-temporal graph neural networks for predictive learning in urban computing: A survey. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* (2023).
- [17] Ming Jin, Shiyu Wang, Lintao Ma, Zhixuan Chu, James Y Zhang, Xiaoming Shi, Pin-Yu Chen, Yuxuan Liang, Yuan-Fang Li, Shirui Pan, et al. 2023. Time-llm: Time series forecasting by reprogramming large language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.01728* (2023).
- [18] Evangelos Kalampokis, Efthimios Tambouris, and Konstantinos Tarabanis. 2011. Open government data: A stage model. In *Electronic Government: 10th IFIP WG 8.5 International Conference, EGOV 2011, Delft, The Netherlands, August 28–September 2, 2011. Proceedings 10*. Springer, 235–246.
- [19] Areti Karamanou, Petros Brimos, Evangelos Kalampokis, and Konstantinos Tarabanis. 2024. Explainable Graph Neural Networks: An Application to Open Statistics Knowledge Graphs for Estimating House Prices. *Technologies* 12, 8 (2024). doi:10.3390/technologies12080128
- [20] Areti Karamanou, Evangelos Kalampokis, and Konstantinos Tarabanis. 2023. Integrated statistical indicators from Scottish linked open government data. *Data in Brief* 46 (2023), 108779.
- [21] Anwar Khan, Mostafa M. Fouda, Dinh-Thuan Do, Abdulaziz Almaleh, and Atiq Ur Rahman. 2023. Short-Term Traffic Prediction Using Deep Learning Long Short-Term Memory: Taxonomy, Applications, Challenges, and Future Trends. *IEEE Access* 11 (2023), 94371–94391. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3309601
- [22] Alexander Kirillov, Eric Mintun, Nikhila Ravi, Hanzi Mao, Chloe Rolland, Laura Gustafson, Tete Xiao, Spencer Whitehead, Alexander C Berg, Wan-Yen Lo, et al. 2023. Segment anything. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 4015–4026.
- [23] Ibai Lana, Javier Del Ser, Manuel Velez, and Eleni I. Vlahogianni. 2018. Road Traffic Forecasting: Recent Advances and New Challenges. *IEEE Intelligent*

(a) Visualization of prediction results for the forecasting horizon of 3 hours for sensor MS106.

(b) Visualization of prediction results for the forecasting horizon of 3 hours for sensor MS108.

Figure 3: Forecasting results of fine-tuned Lag-llama on sensors MS106 and MS108 on the entire test set. We extracted the median forecasts from the probability distribution for depicting the results on the entire test set.

Transportation Systems Magazine 10, 2 (2018), 93–109. doi:10.1109/MITS.2018.2806634

[24] Guofa Li, Weijian Lai, Xiaoxuan Sui, Xiaohang Li, Xingda Qu, Tingru Zhang, and Yuezhi Li. 2020. Influence of traffic congestion on driver behavior in post-congestion driving. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* 141 (2020), 105508.

- [25] Yuxuan Liang, Haomin Wen, Yuqi Nie, Yushan Jiang, Ming Jin, Dongjin Song, Shirui Pan, and Qingsong Wen. 2024. Foundation models for time series analysis: A tutorial and survey. In *Proceedings of the 30th ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. 6555–6565.
- [26] Chenxi Liu, Sun Yang, Qianxiong Xu, Zhishuai Li, Cheng Long, Ziyue Li, and Rui Zhao. 2024. Spatial-temporal large language model for traffic prediction. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.10134* (2024).
- [27] Yisheng Lv, Yanjie Duan, Wenwen Kang, Zhengxi Li, and Fei-Yue Wang. 2014. Traffic flow prediction with big data: A deep learning approach. *Ieee transactions on intelligent transportation systems* 16, 2 (2014), 865–873.
- [28] Michael Mac Kinnon, Shupeng Zhu, Marc Carreras-Sospedra, James V Soukup, Donald Dabdub, GS Samuelsen, and Jacob Brouwer. 2019. Considering future regional air quality impacts of the transportation sector. *Energy Policy* 124 (2019), 63–80.
- [29] Alec Radford, Jong Wook Kim, Chris Hallacy, Aditya Ramesh, Gabriel Goh, Sandhini Agarwal, Girish Sastry, Amanda Askell, Pamela Mishkin, Jack Clark, et al. 2021. Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision. In *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 8748–8763.
- [30] Colin Raffel, Noam Shazeer, Adam Roberts, Katherine Lee, Sharan Narang, Michael Matena, Yanqi Zhou, Wei Li, and Peter J Liu. 2020. Exploring the limits of transfer learning with a unified text-to-text transformer. *Journal of machine learning research* 21, 140 (2020), 1–67.
- [31] Kashif Rasul, Arjun Ashok, Andrew Robert Williams, Arian Khorasani, George Adamopoulos, Rishika Bhagwatkar, Marin Biloš, Hena Ghonia, Nadhir Vincent Hassen, Anderson Schneider, et al. 2023. Lag-llama: Towards foundation models for time series forecasting. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.08278* (2023).
- [32] Kashif Rasul, Calvin Seward, Ingmar Schuster, and Roland Vollgraf. 2021. Autoregressive denoising diffusion models for multivariate probabilistic time series forecasting. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*. PMLR, 8857–8868.
- [33] Konstantinos I Roumeliotis and Nikolaos D Tselikas. 2023. Chatgpt and open-ai models: A preliminary review. *Future Internet* 15, 6 (2023), 192.
- [34] Zezhi Shao, Zhao Zhang, Fei Wang, and Yongjun Xu. 2022. Pre-training enhanced spatial-temporal graph neural network for multivariate time series forecasting. In *Proceedings of the 28th ACM SIGKDD conference on knowledge discovery and data mining*. 1567–1577.
- [35] Md Fahim Sikder, Resmi Ramachandranpillai, and Fredrik Heintz. 2023. Transfusion: generating long, high fidelity time series using diffusion models with transformers. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.12667* (2023).
- [36] Chenxi Sun, Hongyan Li, Yaliang Li, and Shenda Hong. 2023. TEST: Text prototype aligned embedding to activate LLM’s ability for time series. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.08241* (2023).
- [37] Ratchanon Toncharoen and Mongkut Piantanakulchai. 2018. Traffic state prediction using convolutional neural network. In *2018 15th International Joint Conference on Computer Science and Software Engineering (JCSSE)*. IEEE, 1–6.
- [38] Hugo Touvron, Thibaut Lavril, Gautier Izacard, Xavier Martinet, Marie-Anne Lachaux, Timothée Lacroix, Baptiste Rozière, Naman Goyal, Eric Hambro, Faisal Azhar, et al. 2023. Llama: Open and efficient foundation language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2302.13971* (2023).
- [39] Ruey S Tsay. 2005. *Analysis of financial time series*. John Wiley & sons.
- [40] MJ UN. 2018. 68% of the world population projected to live in urban areas by 2050, says UN. *Department of Economic and Social Affairs* (2018).
- [41] A Vaswani. 2017. Attention is all you need. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (2017).
- [42] Billy M Williams and Lester A Hoel. 2003. Modeling and forecasting vehicular traffic flow as a seasonal ARIMA process: Theoretical basis and empirical results. *Journal of transportation engineering* 129, 6 (2003), 664–672.
- [43] Zou Bo Xian, Liu Qiang, et al. 2002. Arma-based traffic prediction and overload detection of network [j]. *Journal of Computer Research and Development* 12 (2002).
- [44] Lun Zhang, Qiuchen Liu, Wenchen Yang, Nai Wei, and Decun Dong. 2013. An improved k-nearest neighbor model for short-term traffic flow prediction. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences* 96 (2013), 653–662.
- [45] Ling Zhao, Yujiao Song, Chao Zhang, Yu Liu, Pu Wang, Tao Lin, Min Deng, and Haifeng Li. 2019. T-GCN: A temporal graph convolutional network for traffic prediction. *IEEE transactions on intelligent transportation systems* 21, 9 (2019), 3848–3858.
- [46] Ge Zheng, Wei Koong Chai, Jing-Lin Duanmu, and Vasilis Katos. 2023. Hybrid deep learning models for traffic prediction in large-scale road networks. *Information Fusion* 92 (2023), 93–114. doi:10.1016/j.inffus.2022.11.019
- [47] Tian Zhou, Peisong Niu, Liang Sun, Rong Jin, et al. 2023. One fits all: Power general time series analysis by pretrained lm. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 36 (2023), 43322–43355.
- [48] Zhaoyang Zhu, Weiqi Chen, Rui Xia, Tian Zhou, Peisong Niu, Bingqing Peng, Wenwei Wang, Hengbo Liu, Ziqing Ma, Qingsong Wen, et al. 2023. eForecaster: Unifying electricity forecasting with robust, flexible, and explainable machine learning algorithms. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, Vol. 37. 15630–15638.